

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE NEW ROLE OF THE TEACHER IN SCHOOL

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Abstract

Today, modern society is at the stage of rapid technological, social and economic transformation, which directly affects the education system. Pedagogy, as the basis of education, is undergoing a radical transformation and is transforming into an interdisciplinary science that combines different fields.

The paper discusses the modern challenges of pedagogy and the innovative approaches that are necessary for the formation of a student-centered, flexible and inclusive learning process.

Special attention is paid to the development of critical thinking, the impact of artificial intelligence on the learning environment and the technological challenges that contribute to the consideration of individual needs.

The article analyzes the reasons why traditional methods are no longer sufficient to meet the requirements of the modern education system, and presents innovation as an important factor in improving the quality of education. The paper aims to popularize new perspectives that will help teachers implement effective and modern teaching models.

Keywords: student, pedagogy, teacher, education.

Introduction

Today, society is facing rapid technological, social and economic changes, which significantly affect the education system and, consequently, pedagogy. People working in the field of education have to not only transfer educational content, but also adapt teaching methods to new requirements, and integrate them with digital technologies.

Challenges such as intercultural communication, globalization, the impact of artificial intelligence, the development of critical thinking and teaching methods tailored to the needs of students require the introduction of new approaches and the improvement of pedagogical practices. Accordingly, pedagogy is no longer just a traditional discipline of knowledge transfer, but has transformed into an interdisciplinary direction that combines psychology, technology, management, social sciences, and others.

The modern education system faces serious challenges that cannot be answered by traditional methods. In particular, the lack of motivation of students, the level of stress, and the lack of an individual approach to the personality constantly raise questions. Today, education involves not only the transfer of knowledge, but also the development of precisely those skills that are necessary in the 21st century labor market. Accordingly, technologies that are used as the basis for creating individualized curricula attach great importance to assessing students' progress.

Innovation in pedagogy plays an important role, as it creates new opportunities, effective approaches, and an environment tailored to needs, so that the learning process becomes more flexible, inclusive, and adaptive. Innovative approaches help students manage their feelings and emotions. Here, the main challenges and approaches of modern pedagogy are analyzed, which contribute to improving the quality of education and offering the next generation a better learning experience.

Main literature

The word "pedagogy" comes from Greek, it is the science of human upbringing and education. Initially, this term meant only the upbringing of children. Over time, the term acquired a broader meaning, and eventually pedagogy refers to the scientific direction of education and teaching. Pedagogy, as a science of education, has a centuries-old history. Its development was closely related to changes in public life, culture and philosophy.

The foundation of pedagogy was laid in ancient civilizations, where education was mainly based on religious and practical knowledge. The role of the Greeks, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, in the formation of pedagogy is also worth noting. Socrates, who tried to develop critical thinking in students using the method of dialogue. When we talk about pedagogy, we should mention the reformers of the 16th and 18th centuries, Johann Comenius, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Johann Pestalozzi. Johann Comenius was one of the first to develop a systematic approach to pedagogy and principles of teaching adapted to the age of the child. Jean-Jacques Rousseau argued that education should be in harmony with nature. Johann Pestalozzi emphasized a humane approach, a child-centered teaching method. As for Georgian pedagogy, which is a bearer of unique traditions and rich educational experience, its roots go back to ancient times and have been developing for centuries. In the early period, education was mainly associated with churches and monasteries. Georgian schools functioned in Shiomghvime, Ikalto, Gelati and other famous monastic centers. The Gelati and Ikalto academies (XI-XII centuries) developed into centers of higher education, where theology, philosophy, natural sciences and philology were studied. Also worth noting are the educational reforms of Vakhtang VI (18th century), which aimed at the development of secular education. We should also mention Ilia Chavchavadze,

Akaki Tsereteli, Iakob Gogebashvili. Iakob Gogebashvili's "Mother Language" became one of the main sources of education for the new generation, which was based on an innovative method of alphabetic teaching. Georgian pedagogy has a centuries-old history and continues to develop today.

Modern education is multifaceted, responding to a changing environment. In the 21st century, technological progress, social changes, and the results of new research influence pedagogical practice. Pedagogy, which responds to these changes, undergoes reforms, and the importance of individual approaches in this process is increasingly growing.

The integration of digital technologies in education is one of the most pressing issues. Pandemia has shown that distance learning can be effective, but it comes with significant challenges, such as low levels of student engagement, lack of digital skills, and problems with technical infrastructure. Artificial intelligence and data analysis allow us to create an individualized learning plan for each student. Technologies have changed the way students receive information, which is why teachers must be able to use them. Modern pedagogy contributes to creating equal opportunities for all students. Although inclusive education is recognized by law in Georgia, schools often do not have sufficient resources and qualified staff to create an inclusive learning environment.

Teachers' qualifications and motivation are crucial for the quality of education. It is necessary for teachers to be constantly updated with modern teaching methods, although professional development programs in Georgia are still not sufficiently developed. Also, the teaching profession is not yet prestigious and highly paid, which prevents the attraction of new staff.

Modern pedagogy is actively looking for innovative ways to increase student engagement. Traditional educational methods are often focused on lecture-based methods, which are based on the first level of Bloom's Taxonomy. Problem-based learning, case studies, discussions/debates, and the like are less used in schools. Today, when information is easily accessible, teachers should use interactive and technology-based methods more.

The development of the education sector largely depends on resources. In some regions of Georgia, schools are physically outdated and do not meet modern standards. Better management is desirable so that funds are spent effectively on improving the educational process. The Georgian system is trying to come into line with European standards. Many perspectives can be considered for the development of education in Georgia, such as:

- Creating a favorable environment for digital learning.
- Using problem-based and interactive teaching methods.
- Providing continuous education and training for teachers.
- Improving infrastructure and increasing learning resources.
- Sharing best practices from European and other countries.

Despite the existing challenges, with the right policy and strategy, Georgian pedagogy will be able to become flexible and adapted to the needs of modern society.

Research Methodology

The study used qualitative research, in-depth interviews with semi-structured questions with 15 school teachers and administrators to study the current state of the education sector in detail.

The study revealed several important findings that reflect the challenges and development opportunities of modern education. Despite the fact that the integration of technology in education is one of the main priorities, a significant part of teachers still lack distance learning skills. Most teachers confirmed in the survey that they need additional training in inclusive education, critical thinking teaching methods, and digital pedagogy. The study also showed that traditional educational methods are still being used in schools, which reduces student motivation and hinders the development of creative skills, although the Georgian education system is trying to get closer to international standards.

Based on the results of the study, several recommendations were developed to promote the effective use of modern teaching methods and technologies by schools. The state should ensure the implementation of initiatives supporting digital education and equipping it with the necessary technical resources. Accordingly, the challenges of modern education require new approaches and strategies in pedagogy.

Summary

The Georgian education system faces many challenges, including general education institutions, which require a timely and effective response. It is necessary to introduce innovative teaching methods, continuous professional development of teachers, and improve technological infrastructure. The problems identified as a result of the study show that increasing student motivation and developing practical skills are of paramount importance.

Modern challenges of pedagogy in Georgian reality require a comprehensive and systematic approach. Despite the existing problems, modern pedagogy must be flexible, innovative, and adaptable to the changing environment. Technological progress, professional development of teachers, and promotion of inclusive education are the main tasks that determine the quality of future education.

Strengthening the Georgian education system requires not only a flexible and strategic approach of state policy, but also the active involvement of society, the private sector, and international partners. Only through joint efforts is it possible to create an educational environment that promotes both personal and societal progress.

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